

The Monastery of Saint Phoibammon in the Rock/ Phoibammon I

Secondary source

Entered by Alexandra Konstantinidou

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Christianity, Christian, Religious Group, Egypt, Monastery, Indo-European, Early Christian Monasticism in Egypt, Language, Religious Place, Afro-Asiatic

Deep in the mountainous desert between the village of Jeme in Western Thebes and the pagarchy capital Hermonthis, lies the monastic settlement that the local inscriptions call the 'Laura' or 'Topos' of Apa Phoibammon. The place is situated eight kilometres from the Nile and 10 kilometers south of the northern Topos of Apa Phoibammon, on the terraces of Deir el- Bahari, and the Holy Topos of Apa Epiphanius. The monks chose not to settle in the Pharaonic tombs of the necropolis of Western Thebes, but they erected a cluster of buildings at the end of a narrow wadi with an abrupt cliff face, about twenty-five meters high, creating a natural semicircular amphitheater for the settlement. It is probable that this monastery was built from the beginning on an empty spot and that the unearthed ruins correspond to its initial plan. On the south side, the settlement was enclosed by a group of buildings. A gatehouse in the southeast served as the central entrance to the community. A church (or oratory) was located to the west, after entering the complex. It was paved with stones and housed the barrel vault tomb of a monk, identified as the superior of the community. The walls were plastered with lime and show signs of red dipinti and simple figural paintings. The monastery was equipped with seven circular bread ovens ranging between 0.50 and 1.20 m high. Provisions were stored in food in three silos on the northeast side. It has been argued that the term 'laura' that refers to the small monastery of Phoibammon does not actually designate a conglomerate of autonomous hermitages. Bachatly who excavated the site considered that it was founded as part of the Pachomian federation. Despite the fact that this view has been contested, recent discussions have concluded that a cenobitic community was most likely installed there, while the term 'laura' was probably introduced by someone from Palestine or Syria. Based on ceramic evidence, the settlement was inhabited in the fourth century. It was at least partially abandoned by the end of the sixth or the beginning of the seventh century, probably due to rockfalls from the mountain that the buildings were attached. However, such a catastrophic event remains just a hypothesis. It is known that Patriarch Damian asked Abraham who used to be the oikonomos of the monastery to move in a less isolated place. As a result of this request, Abraham founded the cenobitic Monastery of Saint Phoibammon (Phoibammon II) in the ruins of the Hatshepsut temple in Deir el-Bahari.

Date Range: 350 CE - 600 CE

Region: The Monastery of Saint Phoibammon in the Rock/ Phoibammon I

Region tags: Egypt, Thebes

Monastery of Saint Phoibammon in the Rock/ Phoibammon I

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

– Rock face

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: No

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

– Other [specify]: According to a hypothesis it was destroyed by rockfalls from the mountain.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saint Phoibammon

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bachatly, C. 1950. Thèbes. Le monastère de Phoibammon. *Chronique d'Égypte* 25 : 167-169.
- Source 2: Khater, A. and O. H. E. KHS-Burmester. 1981. Le monastère de Phoibammon dans la Thebaïde vol. 1. *Archéologie du site*. Cairo.
- Source 3: Krueger, F. 2020. Revisiting the First Monastery of Apa Phoibammon. A Prosopography and Relative Chronology of its Connections to the Monastery of Apa Ezekiel Within the Monastic Network of Hermonthis During the 6th Century. *Archiv für Papyrusforschung und verwandte Gebiete* 66/1: 150-191.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/place/61074>
- Source 1 Description: Trismegistos. An interdisciplinary portal of the ancient world.
- Source 2 URL: <https://4care-skos.mf.no/4care-sites/63/>
- Source 2 Description: DEChriM Database

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1947-1949

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Thebes. The Monastery of Phoibammon.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: It is situated in the desert of western Thebes.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bachatly, C. 1950. Thèbes. Le monastère de Phoibammon. *Chronique d'Égypte* 25 : 167-169.
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Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

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Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1947-1949

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Thebes. The Monastery of Phoibammon.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

- Mountain
- Rock face

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: It is situated in the desert of western Thebes.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳

A single structure

– No

↳

One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

↳

A group of structures:

– Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Yes

- ↳ A group of features:
 - No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - No

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Collapsed

 - ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - Other [specify]: No

 - ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Natural phenomena

–Other [specify]: According to a hypothesis it was destroyed by rockfalls from the mountain.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Saint Phoibammon

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:
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Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:
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– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Dipinti

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: Unspecified

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Simple geometric motifs

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: A graffito explains how soldiers pursued someone (unnamed, because the graffito is damaged) and he found sanctuary inside the monastery. Other graffiti record the presence of refugees living with the monks.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Attached to a rocky mountain in the desert.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Rooms, silos, ovens.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mud-bricks, fired bricks

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Attached to a rocky mountain in the desert.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mud-bricks, fired bricks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

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↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

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Notes: Dipinti

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↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

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– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

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↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: A graffito explains how soldiers pursued someone (unnamed, because the graffito is damaged) and he found sanctuary inside the monastery. Other graffiti record the presence of refugees living with the monks.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:
– No

Are pilgrimages present:
– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
–I don't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– I don't know

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes
Notes: Liturgy, prayer

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Inside the church of the monastery there is a barrel vault tomb of a monk, identified as the superior of the community.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

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↳ Family tomb/crypt:

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↳ Domestic context:
Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Inside the church of the monastery there is a barrel vault tomb of a monk, identified as the superior of the community.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
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↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
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↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
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↳ Are they other:
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Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes
Notes: Liturgy, prayer

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
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–Other [specify]: No

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Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

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Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– I don't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Notes: In a dipinto painted on the west side of the circular cliff, Abraam invoked the founder of the community: "Holy Apa Phoibammon, the martyr, inside the Rock. Pray for me, I, Abraam."

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Notes: Ostraca

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Prayers

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

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Notes: Male

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↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

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– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Notes: In a dipinto painted on the west side of the circular cliff, Abraam invoked the founder of the community: "Holy Apa Phoibammon, the martyr, inside the Rock. Pray for me, I, Abraam."

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:
– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:
– Yes
Notes: Ostraca

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Prayers